

NUMERICAL OPTIMISATION OF MOULD TEMPERATURE REGIME IN RTM PROCESS

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SUMMARY : The aim of the present study is to find the optimal temperature distributions of the temperature field in different phases of the RTM process, i.e. heating and curing in order to minimize the residual non-mechanical stress/strain field induced in the laminate during the process. The mould is heated (cured) in the chamber having located at different points sources of heat being our design variables. The governing equations of the resin flow process and kinetics of it are presented and discussed. Some results of the numerical simulations with the use of the FLUENT package are shown herein as well as the results of the optimization.

KEYWORDS: Optimization, RTM Process, Residual Stress/ Strains, Numerical Simulations, Resin Flow

INTRODUCTION

Resin transfer moulding (RTM) is a process in which resin is injected into a heated mould preloaded with fibrous reinforcement. It is crucial for the mechanical properties of a product that complete impregnation of the fiber is accomplished with no internal stresses/ strains arising during the heating and subsequent curing process. Since the mould geometry is complicated, a relationship between the resin flow and the process variables cannot be obtained analytically. Under the term the process variables we understand various factors, such as: (i) a number and positions of resin inlets, (ii) time of heating and curing process, (iii) locations and temperature of heating points being outside the mould.

Since in the correct and consistent numerical analysis it is necessary to consider resin flow process together with the chemical reactions occurring in the heating process the classical finite difference or finite element procedures cannot be applicable to the tracing of flow front and temperature distributions. In order to circumvent the above problems (especially with the regeneration of meshes at each time step) the control volume finite element method (CV FEM) have been developed. For our purposes the well-known package called FLUENT have been used.

The optimization problem of the RTM process is a complex task where various problems should be taken into account, modelled and then solved. In general, those problems may be classified into for different groups:

- 1) the appropriate physical modelling of the problem that should be consistent with the experimental results,
- 2) the numerical modelling that must be simple enough in order to incorporate into optimization algorithm,
- 3) the formulation of the objectives of optimization problems in view of the existent technological process of components made of fibre reinforced plastics,
- 4) building of the optimization algorithm that must be simple and effective in view of the analysed class of problems.

The present work is just devoted to the discussion of various problems that are encountered in solving (in theoretical and numerical manner) of the above-mentioned problems. With respect

to the above we intend to point out different approaches that may be (or are) commonly used in this area as well as to demonstrate also they limitations.

GOVERNING RELATIONS

The RTM process is commonly divided into two phases: (1) heating of the mould filled with a resin and fibrous reinforcement and (2) curing of a product. From the point of view of technological aspects of the process almost everything is well-known with respect to the chemical and mechanical behaviour of various resins and fibers. However, the knowledge of the technological problems does not prevent arising of internal stresses/ strains in products and of local micro-defects in the matrix and/or at the matrix/fibres interface. The theoretical modelling allows us to understand better various problems (some of them are still open) and in this way to modell the whole process in order to obtain the better composite components.

The equations representing the resin flow consists of the following components:

a) mass conservation equation:
$$\frac{\rho}{\rho_0} + \frac{\rho}{\rho_0} (\mathbf{r} \mathbf{u}_i) = 0 \quad (1)$$

b) momentum conservation equation:
$$\frac{\rho}{\rho_0} (\mathbf{r} \mathbf{u}_j) + \frac{\rho}{\rho_0} (\mathbf{r} \mathbf{u}_i \mathbf{u}_j) = \frac{\rho}{\rho_0} \mathbf{t}_{ij} - \frac{\rho}{\rho_0} \mathbf{p} + \mathbf{r} \mathbf{g}_j + F_j \quad (2)$$

c) energy equation:

$$\frac{\rho}{\rho_0} (\mathbf{r} \mathbf{h}) + \frac{\rho}{\rho_0} (\mathbf{r} \mathbf{u}_i \mathbf{h}) = \frac{\rho}{\rho_0} \left(\mathbf{I} \frac{\rho}{\rho_0} \right) - \frac{\rho}{\rho_0} \sum_j h_j \mathbf{G}_{ji} + \frac{\rho}{\rho_0} \mathbf{p} - \mathbf{t}_{ik} \frac{\rho}{\rho_0} + h_s \quad (3)$$

where:

$$\mathbf{t}_{ij} = m \left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_0} \mathbf{u}_i + \frac{\rho}{\rho_0} \mathbf{u}_j \right) - \frac{2}{3} m \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_i}{\partial x_i} \mathbf{d}_{ij}, \quad (4)$$

ρ - fluid density; [kg/m³], t - time, [s]; u_i - velocity component, [m/s]; μ - molecular fluid viscosity coefficient, [kg/ms]; p - static pressure, [Pa]; g_j - gravity, [m/s²]; F_j external body forces, [kg/m²s²]; h_j - enthalpy of species j , [J/kg]; \mathbf{I} - thermal conductivity, [W/mK]; G_{ji} - flux of species j in the i -th, direction, [kg/s]; h_s - source term, [J/kg]; T - temperature, [K]; $i, j = 1, 2, 3$. The above general relations describing flow of the resin has to be supplemented by the equations characterizing the rheokinetics of the resin in the sense of the viscosity relations:

d) viscosity
$$\mathbf{h} = B \exp\left(\frac{T_b}{T}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{\mathbf{a}_g}{\mathbf{a}_g - \mathbf{a}}\right)^{C_1 + C_2 \mathbf{a}} \quad (5)$$

e) curing rate
$$\frac{d\mathbf{a}}{dt} = (k_1 + k_2 \mathbf{a}^m) \cdot (1 - \mathbf{a})^n, \quad k_i = A_i e^{\frac{-E_i}{RT}}, \quad i=1,2 \quad (6)$$

f) Darcy' s law
$$u_i = \frac{[K]}{\mathbf{h}} (\nabla p)_i \quad (7)$$

where : B, C_1, C_2, T_b - constants; T - the absolute temperature.; $\mathbf{a}_g = 0.65$ (65% of cured material) ; \mathbf{a} - degree of curing, [%] ; m, n - constants; k_i - reaction rate constants; A_i -

pre-exponential factors; E_i - activation energies; R - the universal gas constant, $[K]$ - the permeability tensor.

According to this model a degree of curing at time t is defined as: $\mathbf{a} = \frac{H(t)}{H_\Sigma}$ where $H(t)$ -

heat of reaction released at time t , and H_Σ - total heat of reaction.

Dependly on the used model the coefficient k_i may be identically equal to zero (the model Bogetti, Gillespie) [1] or not.

The set of governing equations (1)-(7) is supplemented by the boundary and initial conditions formulated at the resin inlet, at the boundaries of the mould and at the free surface of the resin filling the mould.

MODELLING OF THE LAMINATE NON-MECHANICAL STRAINS

The non-mechanical strains induced into fibres during the process cycle are composed of two parts: (1) chemical strains, (2) thermal strains. Both of them results in the arising of residual stresses in the product and may be high enough to cause matrix cracking or fibres debonding even before mechanical loading (Donner, Novak) [2]. Finally, it may result in the significant decrease of static (fatigue) strength and on the other hand a possible microcracking exposes fibres to chemical degradation.

In modelling of the above process it is assumed that the chemical strains may be induced in the transverse direction to the fibres and are expressed as follows:

$$e_2^c = \mathbf{b}_1 + \mathbf{b}_2 10^{b_3 a} \quad \mathbf{a} \leq \mathbf{a}^c \quad (8)$$

$$e_2^c = e_2^{cf} \quad \mathbf{a} > \mathbf{a}^c$$

where: e^c the laminate chemical strains, β_1 , β_2 and β_3 are empirical coefficients, α^c is the degree of cure when chemical shrinkage is completed and e_2^{cf} is the final chemical shrinkage strain.

The thermal strains induced in the fibres are defined in a classical way:

$$e_i^T = \mathbf{g}_i \cdot (T - T_0) \quad (9)$$

where γ_i is a thermal expansion coefficient and T_0 is the initial stress free temperature. The transverse modulus dependence on degree of cure α is modeled by the expressions:

$$\bar{E}_{2i}(\mathbf{a}) = E \quad \mathbf{a} < \mathbf{a}^* \quad (10)$$

$$\bar{E}_{2i}(\mathbf{a}) = a_0 + a_1 \mathbf{a} + a_2 \mathbf{a}^2 \quad \mathbf{a}^* \leq \mathbf{a}$$

$$\bar{E}_1(\mathbf{a}) = \bar{E}_{11i} + (\bar{E}_{1f} - \bar{E}_{1i}) \cdot \mathbf{a} \quad (11)$$

$$\bar{\mathbf{n}}_{12}(\mathbf{a}) = \bar{\mathbf{n}}_{12i} + (\bar{\mathbf{n}}_{12f} - \bar{\mathbf{n}}_{12i}) \cdot \mathbf{a} \quad (12)$$

The mechanical properties are used to determine the time-dependent stiffnesses, and in this way one may evaluate the induced during the RTM process time-dependent moment resultants arising in the laminate:

positions of heating sources located outside the mould, the values of the temperatures at those points and on many parameters describing the cure kinetics of the problem.

The possible optimization problems may be formulated in two versions *less* and *more general*. As it will be demonstrated below the fundamental difference in both approaches depends on the computational efforts required in the numerical analysis.

The first (less general) optimization problem may be written in the following way:

To find such the temperatures of heat sources T_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, N$) located around the mould that the distributions of the cure parameter \hat{a} inside the mould and of the temperature field are homogeneous, i.e.:

$$\text{MinMax } \hat{a}(x, y, z, t) \quad (14)$$

and

$$\text{MinMax } T(x, y, z, t_j) \quad (15)$$

The total number of heat sources N depends on the practical realisation of the RTM process. Each of the heating points has the temperature equal to T_i being the design variables in our problem. The external temperature field is written as the continuous function with the use of the cubic, B spline functions, i.e.:

$$T(s) = \sum_{i=1}^N T_i B_i(s) \quad (16)$$

where s is a length parameter of the curve drawn around the mould boundaries. One may introduce additional than T_i design variables in the sense of the total number and positions of injection gates. The optimization problem given by eqn (16) presents the requirements with respect to the prescribed heating regime in the RTM process. Commonly the heating process is represented by the temperature versus time curve and the example of such a curve is plotted in Fig. 32

It should be emphasized that the optimal distributions (15),(16) does not correspond to the flat planes since it very difficult to obtain at each nodal point the identical value of the functionals \hat{a} and T at each time steps t_j . Therefore, it is assumed that the solution is optimal as the following condition is satisfied:

$$U_l \leq U_k(s) \leq U_u, k = 1, 2, \dots, K \quad (17)$$

where:

$$U_l = (1 - \mathbf{a})U_{aver}, \quad U_u = (1 + \mathbf{a})U_{aver}, \quad U_{aver} = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K U_k(s) \quad (18)$$

\hat{a} is a parameter defining the range of acceptance of the optimal solutions. In general, it is assumed that its value should be less or equal 0.05. $U_k(x, y, z, t)$ denotes the value of the objective functionals (\hat{a} or T) evaluated at the nodal point k .

It is worth to mention also that the optimization problem is formulated as the *MinMax* one in order to equalize the values of the objective U over the whole plane and it differs qualitatively from the typical formulations leading to the limitation of the functional value ,i.e.: $\max U(s) \leq U_{admis}$, where U_{admis} denotes the admissible, prescribed *a priori* value of the functional.

Having the homogeneous distributions of the objectives U the final objective functional may be written as follows:

To find such a temperature regime (the example of that is plotted in Fig.2) in the RTM process that minimizes the residual stresses given by eqn (13), i.e.:

$$\text{Min } M(t) \quad (19)$$

Since both the cure parameter α and the temperature field T may vary during the RTM process the second (more general) optimization problem may be presented in the following form:

To find such values of the temperatures of the heating points located around the mould that minimizes the residual stresses, i.e.:

$$\text{Min } M(t) \quad (20)$$

It is obvious that now the distributions of the α parameter and the temperature field in time allows to control the RTM process in such a way that minimizes the residual stresses much better than in the case of the constant values required in the optimization problems represented by the relations (14), (15).

The design variables T_i (see eqn (16)) are written in the binary form of the chromosome – each chromosome represents a real number. Then the chromosomes are used in the optimization procedure that are based on the version of genetic algorithms. In the broader formulation of the optimization problem given by eqs (14),(15) and (19) the optimization process should be conducted for each phase of RTM process independently. It means that at each time steps it is necessary to change the external temperature field. For less general optimization problem the external temperature field is assumed to be homogeneous and given in advance, so that it is necessary to analyse the variations of the cure parameter and strain/stresses induced in the laminate with time. Such an analysis have been conducted and the results are presented below.

NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

Fig. 2 The temperature vs. time diagram for the RTM process

Let consider the temperature regime of the RTM process plotted in Fig.2. In order to establish the evolution of the process it is necessary to determine the coordinates of the characteristic points shown in Fig.2. In this sense the optimization process (20) is reduced to the parametric optimization. The parametric studies have been conducted for two variants of the cure models: (1) $k_1 = 0$ in eqn (6) – the analogous example have been solved by Gopal et al. [4] and (2) $k_1 > 0$ in eqn (6). As it may be noticed from the plots presented in Figs 3, 4 different values of

the k_1 parameters results in different behaviour of the curing process and also in different values of the residual stresses arising in the laminate. Comparing with the case analysed by the Gopal et al. [4] one may observe the further reduction of the residual stresses from about 48 Mpa for the first case to 40.8 Mpa in the second case as k_1 is greater than zero. The results point out the very important problem of the theoretical modelling of the RTM process. On the other hand the results show evidently that the homogeneous temperature distribution over the whole mould may lead to the prestressing of the laminate. Thus nonhomogeneous temperature distributions over the mould should be preferred in the further numerical optimization studies.

Fig. 3 Variations of the cure degree

Fig. 4 Variations of the residual stresses with time

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